

THE SEMANTICS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES OF HYPERBOLE/MEIOSIS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHRASEOLOGY

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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the importance of stylistic devices in the English and Uzbek languages including, lexical stylistic devices of Hyperbole and Meiosis and their semantic features while using as the core elements of phraseology. Understanding semantic features of the stylistic devices of Hyperbole and Meiosis can help speakers to make their speeches more colorful and emotional.

Key words: phraseology, hyperbole, meiosis, semantic features, communication.

Phraseology is a branch of linguistics which studies phraseological unities. The term phraseology is used in two ways: 1) the quantity of phraseological unities in a language and 2) the branch (subject) studying these unities. Phraseology comes from Greek “phrases”- expression and “logos”-word and it means the science of phrases that are idioms. Phraseology is a combination of phraseological unities which are the equivalent of a word. They are semantic and structural inseparable word combinations⁴⁸. They possess various features of meaning and usage. Lexicology studies the content of vocabulary and phraseology studies the one of phraseological unities. The language unity in vocabulary is a word; however, idiom is a language unity of phraseology. The vocabulary of any language consists of words and idioms.

Much useful insight into hyperbole may be found in the literature on irony and sarcasm, and, indeed, hyperbole seems to be a recurring phenomenon in ironic utterances. Nearly all idioms of languages carry stylistic meaning not literal meaning. Phraseological units are considered vital elements of each language. There are some hyperbolic phraseologies in English and Uzbek.

⁴⁸ Shoabdurahmonov Sh. and b. The current Uzbek literary language, Tashkent: ziyo ,1980.

Phrasemic verbalizations of Hyperbole in English.	Literal meanings
We have not seen Aunt Sophia <i>for a dog's age</i> for years	It means that we have not seen her a lot of years.
He said the decade after World War II was Canada's golden age	A period of or defined by outstanding excellence, quality, prosperity, or achievement
I have not seen Sam in <i>a coon's age</i>	In a coon's age means in a very long time
Mrs. Joiner is <i>over the hill</i>	Over the hill means very old
If his business becomes successful, I will <i>eat my hat</i> .	Eat my hat used to say that something will not happen or cannot be true
I'd love to buy a Rolls-Royce, but it <i>costs an arm and a leg</i> .	It means extremely expensive
He seems to <i>have money to burn</i> . He always buys his girlfriend extravagant thing.	To be very rich and spend a lot of money on unnecessary things.
She was on cloud nine when he proposed to marry her.	Feel extreme happiness or elation
I love you to the moon and back	To love someone too much
Cry me a river	To cry a lot
You're killing me, Smalls!	Suffering from one's attitude.

Phrasemic verbalizations of Hyperbole In Uzbek	Literal meanings
Boshim ko'kka yetdi	Juda hursand bo'lmoq
Yog' tushsa yalagudek toza	Nihoyatda toza
Qushdek otilib chiqdi.	Shoshilmoq
Yulduzni benarvon uradi.	Ishbilarmon
Osmondagi oyni olib beradi	Ko'p narsani vada bermoq
Uyni boshiga ko'tardi	To'polon qilmoq, shovqin solmoq
Og'zi qulog'iga yetdi	Nihoyatda hursan

Stylistic device of Meiosis which is one of the vital elements of understatement, is implemented in phraseology and it makes our speech more effective and help to avoid offensive situations.

Phrasemic verbalizations of stylistic device of Meiosis in English	Literal meanings
So many years of sacrifice and then you can leave me at the <i>drop of a hat</i> .	Very little time
We don't need someone like him in this company. People with his skills are a <i>dime a dozen</i> these days	Common, inexpensive , and easy to get or available anywhere.
She bought the house <i>for a song</i>	Very cheaply
I'll just <i>take forty winks</i> before getting ready for walk	To take a nap for a short period of time.
<i>Everybody and his cousin</i> will be in line for opening night with free popcorn.	Too many people, a huge crowd
I enjoyed <i>every minute</i> of the match. It was just fantastic	Describing whole period that something lasted
Everything was a calm. But just <i>in a split second</i> a storm hit the whole region causing a lot of victims.	In just short time

In Uzbek it is also common to meet phrasemic expressions with stylistic device of meiosis. Meiosis develops effectiveness and colorfulness of phrasemic expressions.

Phrasemic verbalizations of stylistic device of Meiosis in Uzbek	Literal meaning
Ko'z ochib yumguncha umr o'tib ketyapti.	Juda tez ma'nosini ifodalash
Kiprik qoqquncha kelaman	Tez fursatda ma'nosini ifodalash uchun
Bir nafasda she'r yod oldim.	To'xtamay tezlik bilan
Bir daqiqada yetib kelaman.	Qisqa vaqtni ifodalash uchun
Bir zumda dasturhonda hamma nozu ne'matlar tayyor bo'ldi.	Qisqa vaqtni ifodalash uchun
Bir so'z ham aytmay ketdi	Indamay ketish ma'nosi uchun
Hamrdan qinni sug'urgandek	Juda onson, mashshaqatsiz

In both English and Uzbek, stylistic devices of hyperbole and meiosis are utilized in idiomatic expressions. They made conversations more beautiful and efficient.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Арнольд И.В. Стилистика современного английского языка. – Москва, 1973.
2. Кунин А.В. Гипербола в сфере английской фразеологии (О фразеологической гиперболе)// Английская фразеология в функциональном аспекте. – Москва: ВАСХНИЛ. Вып, 336,1989. – С. 85–93
3. Kukharensko V.A. A Book of Practice in Stylistics. – М.: Высшая школа, 1986. –356 с.
4. Ferré G. Multimodal Hyperbole. Multimodal Communication,(1). doi:10.1515/mc-20140003., 2014
5. Galperin I.R. Stylistics. Moscow: Higher school, 1981. -P. 289.
6. Heidi Shelton Jenck. Teaching About Hyperbole Guest.Longman: London,1992.- P. 267.
7. Wales Katie. A Dictionary of Stylistics. Pearson Education, 2001.- P. 315.